

NOTES

Oxidation of Hydrazine by Vanadium (V)

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With respect to the oxidation of hydrazine, vanadium (V) has been stated¹ to show behaviour intermediate between those of typical one-equivalent and two-equivalent oxidants corresponding to equations (i) and (ii)

In continuation of our interest in the potentiometric studies of multivalent oxidations the present work was taken up. Investigations have been carried out in neutral as well as sulphuric media.

Standard solutions of vanadium (V) and hydrazine were prepared in re-distilled water using analar grade sodium metavanadate and B.D.H. hydrazine sulphate respectively and standardised with Mohr's salt² and KIO_3 solutions. Potentiometric investigations were made by a modified procedure as described by Prasad and Ojha⁴. Reaction mixtures were stored at room temperature for various periods; in some cases they were heated upto 90° and then stored. E.m.f.'s in each case were recorded at room temperature.

Reactions are relatively faster in neutral than in acidic solutions and a conventional potentiometric titration is possible in the former case. In neutral solutions the colour of the reaction mixtures turned bright green while in acidic media it was blue.

TABLE

A. Hydrazine solution added to 10 ml. of NaVO_3

Concentration of N_2H_4	Concentration of V(V)	Concentration of H_2SO_4	Temp. & period of storage	Colour of the mixtures	Points of inflexion	Moles of N_2H_4 /mole of V(V)
0.1M	0.005M	1.0N	Room temp./ 24 hrs.	Blue	0.5	1.0
0.1M	0.01M	1.0N	90°C/24 hrs.	Blue	0.5 1.0 2.0	0.5 1.0 2.0
0.1M	0.01M	1.0N	Room temp./ (30°C) 9 days	Blue	0.3 1.2 2.1	0.3 1.2 2.1
0.1M	0.01M	neutral	Room temp./ 24 hrs.	Dark green	1.0	0.5

B. Vanadate solution added to 10 ml. of N_2H_4

Concentration of N_2H_4	Concentration of V(V)	Concentration of H_2SO_4	Temp. & period of storage	Colour of the mixtures	Points of inflexion	Moles of V(V)/mole of N_2H_4
0.01M	0.1M	1.0N	90°C/24 hrs.	Green to Blue	1.0	1.0
					1.8	1.8
					3.6	3.6
0.01M	0.025M	neutral	Room temp. (30°C)/24 hrs.	Green	2.0	0.5

In neutral or very low acidic ($< 0.01N$) medium, 0.5 mole of N_2H_4 are used up per mole of vanadium (V) irrespective of the order of addition of the reactants and a correspondingly sharp inflexion is noticed in the curves. This along with the visual observation points to the following overall two equivalent oxidation-reduction process :

In higher acid concentrations ($> 0.01N$), multiple inflexions indicating stepwise oxidation and reduction occur. Positions of these inflexions depend on the concentration of the mineral acid, period of storage, temperature and the order of the addition of the reactants. Thus when hydrazine is added to the vanadate solution and the mixtures stored for 9 days at room temperature three inflexions are noticed at 0.3, 1.2 and 2.1 moles of the former per mole of the latter (in 1.0N H_2SO_4), indicating lack of simple stoichiometric steps, while these are at 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 moles if they are heated at 90° for an hour and then stored at room temperature for 24 hours. Evidently, simultaneous mixed reactions consisting of both one and two equivalent redox process of the following type might be occurring all of which are not covered by the same equilibrium constant :

2 equiv. process :

1 equiv. process :

and this vitiates reproducibility too. Strictly stoichiometric one equivalent redox reaction [equation (viii)] occurs, however, in highly acidic medium (1.0N) when one mole of hydrazine is used up per mole of vanadium (V).

It is possible that the disproportionation of N_2H_4 is preceded by the formation of $N_2H_3^5$ which subsequently dissociates to give the products. The formation of the blue colour, characteristic of VO^{++} ions, coupled with the fact that the V(IV) is a poor oxidising agent, rules out the formation of diimide (equation ix) by further oxidation N_2H_3 .

In the reverse case, i.e., when V(V) is added to N_2H_4 , the latter can be oxidised successively to N_2H_3 , N_2H_2 , N_2H and finally N_2 ,

Three distinct inflexions were noticed in the curves at 1.0, 1.8 and 3.6 moles of V(V) per mole of hydrazine taken. These values and the absence of the fourth inflexion indicate that there is partial disproportionation of the N_2H_3 formed in the first step,

REFERENCES

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